

Fondazione IMC Centro Marino Internazionale ONLUS

Posidonia beach/dunes socio-economic evaluation

*POSBEMED Activity 3.4
Final Report*

POSBEMED deliverable 3.4.1: Analysis on banquette perception by stakeholders

POSBEMED deliverable 3.4.2: Report on stakeholder expectation and cost-benefit analysis of removal Posidonia banquettes

This report has been developed in the framework of the project POSBEMED - Sustainable management of the systems Posidonia-beaches in the Mediterranean region (Project reference number: 1336) within the Programme Interreg MED (2014-2020), Priority Priority Axis 3: Protecting and promoting Mediterranean natural and cultural resources, 3.2: To maintain biodiversity and natural ecosystems through strengthening the management and networking of protected areas.

Work Package 3

Activity 3.4 Posidonia-beach/dunes socio-economic evaluation

Deliverable 3.4.1 Analysis on banquette perception by stakeholders

Deliverable 3.4.2: Report on stakeholder expectation and cost-benefit analysis of removal Posidonia banquettes

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Citation:

Mossone P., Guala I., Heurtefeux H., Giunta Fornasin M.E., Issaris Y., Gerakaris V., Salomidi M., Milano P., Guido M., Marciano V., Otero M.M., Aljinovic B., Simeone S., 2018. POSBEMED: Posidonia beach/dunes socio-economic evaluation. Final Report. IMC Foundation - International Marine Centre, Technical report 2:2018, 70 pp. + Annexes.

ISBN 9788885983106

Project co-financed by the European
Regional Development Fund

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1. INTRODUCTION

POSBEMED (Sustainable management of the systems of Posidonia-beaches in the Mediterranean region) is a project developed within the Interreg Med program, with the aim of defining a shared strategy for the sustainable management of the beaches on which seagrass banquettes form.

For this purpose, two surveys were conducted, one addressed to beachgoers and the other to public and private stakeholders.

The survey addressed to beachgoers aims at analyzing their perception of and attitudes towards the presence of the banquettes and the ways in which they are managed.

Within this process, an economic analysis of the costs and benefits related to the presence of the banquettes was conducted, in relation to the tourist's choices as a consumer.

The survey addressed the public and private stakeholders' aims at assessing their expectations in relation to the behaviour and choices of tourists. This is both in relation to the presence of seagrass banquettes on the beaches, and in relation to the managerial decisions implemented by local administrations.

We compared certain elements of assessment, considering the opinions of those who use the beach for recreational purposes, those who exploit the beach economically and those who manage it, in order to derive possible strategies for sustainable management from both an environmental and economic point of view.

2. STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTION SURVEY 3.4.1

2.1 METHODOLOGY OF WORK

2.1.1 THE SURVEY

The research methodology was based on what was discussed in the steering committee among POSBEMED partners.

The methodology adopted involves the detection of a random sample, in high season, at a minimum number of selected beaches in Italy (Sardinia, Puglia and other regional destinations), France (PACA), Greece (Chalkidiki, Attica, Chios isl., Lesvos isl., Crete isl.), Cyprus and Spain (Alicante and the Balearic Islands).

Each partner oversaw the completion of a minimum of 200 questionnaires for at least 4 different beaches located in different municipalities. The beaches chosen must be subjected, at least periodically, to banquette deposition. In addition, the partners were requested to select at least 2 beaches with banquette removal and 2 without.

The sample is related to visitors to beaches affected by the formation of banquettes of *Posidonia oceanica*.

The sample size was established in a minimum of 200 interviews for each partner involved, plus a further 200 by the IUCN partner to be carried out in Cyprus.

The total composition of the sample was as follows:

Table 1

Data collected by	Country/Region
IMC	Italy_Sardinia
EcoLogica	Italy_Continent
EID-Med	France
HCMR	Greece
IUCN	Cyprus
IUCN	Spain

Each partner was provided with a survey package that includes three files:

Perception_survey_form_ISTRUCTIONS.docx (Annex 2)

Perception_survey_form_QUESTIONNAIRE.docx

Perception_survey_DATASHEET.xlsx

The questionnaire was divided into sections; the data collected was subdivided into topics, with a subsequent statistical elaboration.

2.1.2 THE SURVEY FORM

The GENERAL DATA section is NOT part of the survey and should be filled in before submitting the questionnaire, in order to record the location.

<p>GENERAL DATA</p> <p>Partner _____</p> <p>Survey form No. ____</p> <p>Date ___/___/___</p> <p>Conservation level over the area:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> National/regional ordinary legislation<input type="checkbox"/> Marine or Coastal Protected Area<input type="checkbox"/> Natura 2000 site <p>Place of survey: _____</p> <p>Municipality: _____</p> <p>Region (Administrative district): _____</p> <p>Country: _____</p>

The GENERAL SECTION is needed to provide demographic and socio-economic data for the interviewee. Questions 5, a, b) aim to distinguish tourists from residents.

GENERAL SECTION

- 1) Age: up to 20; from 20 to 40; from 40 to 60; over 60

- 2) Gender: M F

- 3) Profession:
 - student
 - unemployed
 - employee
 - worker
 - temporary worker
 - self-employed
 - manager
 - businessman

- 4) Level of education:
 - 0 to secondary school
 - high school degree
 - university degree

- 5) Nationality:
 - Same nationality of the survey site
 - Other (specify) _____

- 5a) Is the interviewed a tourist or a local resident?
 - Tourist
 - Local resident

- 5b) If the interviewed person is a tourist, is he/she resident in the same region of the survey site?
 - YES
 - NO

The PERCEPTION SECTION is the central part of the survey. It contains questions relating to positive or negative attitudes towards the presence of banquettes on the beach, the expectation of how they should be managed, the evaluation of the advantages and disadvantages of the presence of banquettes, and the perception of green labels as a useful factor for the awareness and acceptance of seagrass banquettes

PERCEPTION SECTION

1P) How do you consider the presence of banquette of Posidonia on beaches?

Negative		Indifferent		Positive	
1	2	3	4	5	

2P) Is the presence of banquette a relevant choice factor when go to the beach?

- a. YES in a positive sense (I prefer beach with banquette)
- b. NO
- c. YES in a negative sense (I prefer beach without banquette)

3P) In which way do you think the banquette should be managed?

- a. Total removal and disposal for the whole year
- b. Total removal and disposal only in summer season
- c. Temporary removal and repositioning at the end of summer season
- d. Partial removal to avoid excessive accumulations
- e. No removal at all

4P) According to you, the seagrass banquettes have the following advantages (rating from 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree):

- a. If removed, it can be used as a raw material – rating _____
- b. It protects the beach from erosion – rating _____
- c. It is an ecosystem that hosts some organisms important for biodiversity – rating _____
- d. It is a good place to enjoy the beach – rating _____

5P) According to you, the seagrass banquettes have the following disadvantages (rating from 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree):

- a. It emanates an unpleasant smell – rating _____
- b. It makes unpleasant/difficult bathing or swimming in the proximity – rating _____
- c. Bothersome animals live in the banquette – rating _____
- d. The leaves often stick to the body – rating _____
- e. It accumulate debris – rating _____

- 6P) Do you think that a specific green label for natural beaches (no banquettes removal) may help to increase tourists' awareness and acceptance of seagrass banquettes?
- YES
- NO

The EVALUATION SECTION is used to collect the data needed to evaluate the banquettes as an environmental good with the contingent valuation method. This valuation makes up the basis for calculating the benefit-cost analysis of banquette management. In this specific case, we wanted to analyze the situation in which the beaches were kept in a natural state, without the removal of the banquettes.

The instructions for filling out the survey highlight the difficulty involved herein, as well as the difficulty in instructing the surveyors who administer the questionnaire.

EVALUATION SECTION

- 1V) Would you be willing to pay (one-off) to keep this beach for public use and in a state of naturalness, also with any banquettes of Posidonia that should eventually deposit? If yes, what would you be willing to pay?

- | | | | |
|------------------------------|-------------------------------|-------------------------------|-------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 5€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 60€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 140€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 240€ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 10€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 80€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 160€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 250€ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 20€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 100€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 180€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 300€ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 40€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 120€ | <input type="checkbox"/> 200€ | other (specify value) _____ |

- NO

- 2V) If your answer was NO, could you tell us the reasons?
- I would pay for the use of a beach without seagrass banquettes
 - I need more information to make a decision
 - The expense should be borne by the municipality or other Local Government administration
 - I think it is not worth paying to preserve this area
 - I could not bear this expenditure at this time

The AWARENESS SECTION aims to highlight the level of general knowledge regarding the role played by banquettes in keeping the beach in equilibrium; this is then related to opinions about the amount of public information available on the topic.

AWARENESS SECTION

1W) Before this interview, did you ever consider that seagrass such as Posidonia banquettes can be useful for the conservation of beaches and dunes?

YES

NO

2W) Do you think that public information about the ecological role that seagrass banquettes have on beaches/dunes is sufficient?

YES

NO

2.1.3 THE ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Part of the research is intended to provide basic data for the assessment of seagrass banquette as an environmental good.

The main difficulty in assessing environmental assets lies in their nature as non-market public goods.

Public goods have the main characteristics of being non-rivalrous (the use of a good by an individual is not incompatible with use by another individual), and non-excludable (the impossibility, or in any case difficulty, of excluding certain individuals from the use of the good).

Environmental goods are generally non-market goods in that an exchange based on their market value is not possible. This does not mean that they have no economic value, understood as the measurable quantity of use related to that good (Sellar et al. 1986).

In economic terms, the total value of environmental goods (TEV) is a composite value consisting of a sum of the different categories of benefits related to their use or existence.

$$\text{TEV} = \text{Use value} + \text{Non-Use value}$$

The Use Value can be direct when it is determined by the direct human use of natural resources (e.g. timber, fisheries, tourism), or indirect when it is related to the ecological functions that provide support and protection (e.g. protection from floods and erosion, water purification or carbon sequestration).

The Non-Use Value is based on intangible human benefits, not related to the direct or indirect use of the environmental good:

- Existence Value: a value recognized as belonging to the environmental good regardless of any consideration of its ecosystem functions (e.g. endangered species, unknown and unreachable places like the bottom of the oceans).
- Option Value: the value derived from the options related to the availability of the environmental good at present and in the future (e.g. biodiversity).

- Bequest (or legacy) Value: the value stemming from nature conservation for future generations (e.g. avoiding damage from climate change, preserving life conditions, preserving biodiversity).

Methods for assessing environmental goods may or may not be based on an approach that provides for the construction of a demand curve.

The approaches not involving a demand curve are the following:

Damage function:

1. Dose response methods: based on the cost of physiological reactions of humans, plants, and animals to pollution (pollution stress);
2. Replacement or restoration cost: considers the cost of replacing or restoring a damaged property and uses this value as a measure of the benefit of this restoration (e.g. the cost of beach nourishment)
3. Reduction behavior: considers expenses for the prevention of environmental damage and uses this value as a measure of the benefits of avoiding damage (e.g. expenses incurred for a sewage treatment plant)

Opportunity cost (indirect value):

the benefits of the activity that causes degradation of the environment (e.g. the drying of a wetland to allow agriculture) are estimated, to establish a measure of how high the environmental benefits should be in order to make development (agricultural) inconvenient.

Methods based on the construction of a demand curve can be direct or indirect:

- Direct methods (stated preferences) simulate the existence of a market for the environmental good or service. The most common methods involve hedonic prices and travel costs and are based on the evaluation of the value of use ex-post. This is calculated according to the preferences expressed by the consumer through different methods, in order to evaluate the economic effort aimed at the enjoyment of the environmental good.
- Indirect methods (revealed preferences) attribute a monetary value indirectly, through the analysis of changes in the consumption of market goods related to the asset or the environmental service. The most common method is the Contingent Assessment.

The indirect methods, as well as the methods without a demand curve, only allow for the reconstruction of the value of direct use referred to a specific ecosystem service, while the direct methods can capture the whole TEV.

For this reason, the Contingent Assessment method is the most widely-used method for estimating the value of use and non-use of environmental assets jointly (Carson et al. 2001). It is also the most controversial of the non-market valuation methods.

The method of contingent valuation (CVM) is referred to as a "revealed preference" method. The fact that the CVM is based on what people say they would do, rather than on what people have been observed to do, is the source of its greatest strengths and weaknesses.

Specifically, the method consists in requiring consumers to express their willingness to pay (WTP) through interviews or questionnaires.

The method of contingent assessment directly implies asking people, in a survey, how much they would be willing to pay for specific environmental services. In some cases, people are asked the amount of compensation they would be willing to accept to forgo specific environmental services. This is called "contingent" assessment because people are asked to declare their willingness

to pay, based on a specific hypothetical scenario and the description of the ecosystem service in the hypothetical transaction.

The construction of the demand curve is obtained starting from the distribution of the number of people willing to pay for each price.

The shape of the demand curve is obtained by interpolating the data by means of a logarithmic regression, which is more appropriate than linear regression (Sellar et al. 1986). The area under the curve in the interval between the minimum price and the maximum price constitutes the WTP (Randall and Stoll, 1980).

Alternatively, the calculation of the integral can be approximated by means of the discrete values obtained from the sum of the areas of the rectangles obtained by multiplying each price class by the number of responses that express it. This method is less precise if the R^2 value of the interpolation curve is high, but more reliable in the case of very low R^2 values.

Once the value of the WTP has been calculated, this value is multiplied by the conversion factor between the sample and the population.

The main criticisms of the method relate to the credibility, reliability and accuracy of the answers. Credibility refers to the fact that respondents answer the question the interviewer is trying to ask. If respondents answer the question

correctly, reliability refers to cultural variables (or prejudices) that can influence responses. Precision refers to the variability of responses.

Accuracy can be increased with the simple act of increasing the sample size. The problems of credibility or reliability are not reduced by an increase in sample size. They are influenced by the form of the questions, by cultural background and by the specific training of the person doing the survey. Therefore, credibility and reliability must be assessed with particular care when the use of such surveys is linked to the implementation of cost-benefit analysis, the assessment of damage after the verification of responsibility or as general information that influences the legislative process (Diamond and Hausman, 1994).

While the sample is defined at the outset, the population must be considered as the potential demand in case of the full use of the assessed environmental good: in our case, the maximum load capacity of the beach.

To obtain this value, reference was made to the maximum number of users that can occupy the beach at the same time. In particular, we referred to the load capacity of the beaches, as calculated by the Sardinia Region (Carboni and Russino, 2013). In this document, the Sardinia Region estimates that the space each bather can occupy (defined here as space per user) is approximately 3.5 m². This value equals approximately 6.5 m² when a beach has a particular landscape value or is in erosion.

For each beach where the questionnaire was administered, the surface exploited by bathers was estimated as the beach surface extending from the shoreline to the land boundary of the beach itself (e.g. the foot of a dune or cliff, a border of vegetation, a construction). This surface was related to the most conservative user space (6.5 m² per person). The value obtained from this ratio represents the value of the population considered, or in other words, the maximum load capacity of the beach.

The value of WTP for the entire population indicates the value of the benefits granted by the beach in a state of naturalness and unaltered by the removal of the banquettes. This translates into the total amount of money that the surveyed beachgoers are willing to spend in a hypothetical economic transaction, to keep the beaches in a natural state, with the seagrass banquettes as they have been deposited over time.

The valuation of the benefits deriving from the presence of seagrass banquettes has been expressed as a function of the ecosystem service of recreational use for the beach. Therefore, the cost must be evaluated in the same way.

The questionnaire includes the 2P question, which specifically investigates whether the presence of banquettes is a factor in choosing the beach.

The process of assessing the social cost attributable to the presence of seagrass banquettes starts with the quantification of the average expenditure per tourist per unit of time, excluding the trip cost. This is then multiplied by the number of beachgoers surveyed in full-use conditions, and reduced to the percentage share of those who declare the presence of banquette as a negative factor of choice.

2.2 RESULTS 3.4.1

2.2.1 GENERAL SECTION

The section called "GENERAL DATA" is not an integral part of the survey, but is intended to constitute a registry for the traceability of the questionnaires. Conversely, this "GENERAL SECTION" provides the first set of information on the composition of the sample detected.

The data provided shows the composition by age, sex, employment status and education.

The data thus obtained will be used for a disaggregated analysis of the data coming from the other sections.

Figure 1 shows how the beaches studied are frequented mainly by people from the ages of 20 to 40 and 40 to 60, while the extreme classes of age are less present. The category of people under the age of 20 makes up just 8% of the sample surveyed.

Figure 1 – Sample composition by age

The composition by gender (figure 2) shows a rather balanced distribution, with a slight prevalence of the female component.

Figure 2 – Sample composition by gender

The employment status composition (figure 3) finds a clear prevalence of office workers, equal to 32%, compared to all other categories. There is also a strong presence of self-employed workers and students. Pensioners were asked to declare their previous occupation.

Figure 3 – Sample composition by occupation

The composition by level of education (figure 4) sees a prevalence of the university graduates, followed by those with a high-school diploma. This figure is surprising because, given the prevalence of office workers compared to other

categories, it would be reasonable to expect a prevalence of high-school graduates compared to university graduates.

Figure 4 – Sample composition by education

Figures 5 and 6 show the composition of the sample between tourists and residents, with the figure broken down by country. As expected, the largest share of tourists in the sample was found in Greece, followed by Italy. Surprisingly, the lowest share was recorded in France, apparently because the interviews were not carried out at the height of the tourist season.

Figure 5 – Sample composition by the interviewee’s provenance

Figure 6 – Sample composition : tourists and residents by country

2.2.2 PERCEPTION SECTION

The purpose of this section is to evaluate, in different ways, the attitude of beachgoers towards the presence of Posidonia banquettes. In particular, we are trying to understand if this presence is perceived positively or negatively, by whom and what repercussions could result from the managerial decision not to remove them.

In Figure 7 we can see how the general data of the sample shows a fairly large negative perception, even if it does not constitute the majority. It is important to note that, for managerial purposes, those who have a positive attitude and those who are indifferent can be considered as a single category, in the sense that neither of them require the removal of the banquettes. Notice how attitudes tend to polarize at the positive end of the spectrum, and especially at the negative end. In fact, those who express a totally negative or positive position prevail over those who have a less clear position.

Figure 7 – Perception of presence of banquettes: an overview

The disaggregated figure of the perception of the presence of banquettes sees a more radically negative attitude in the most extreme age classes (figure 8). Among the different categories (figure 9), although with a certain balance (the most negative and the least negative make up 21 percentage points), those less tolerant of the presence of Posidonia banquettes on the beach are the office workers and the manual laborers, while the most tolerant appear to be the entrepreneurs and self-employed workers.

Figure 8 – Perception of presence of banquettes by age

Figure 9 – Perception of presence of banquettes by working status

With reference to the level of education (figure 10), the unequivocal data is that tolerance is a direct function of the level of education.

Figure 10 – Perception of presence of banquettes by educational level

Figure 11 shows that between the two classes of phenomena there is a very tight correlation, expressed by a coefficient of determination R^2 which is very close to 1.

Figure 11 – Negative perception of banquettes by educational level

Figure 12 shows the data disaggregated on a national basis. The analysis of the graph shows that only in Italy is the negative attitude lower than the average data of the sample (the negative average is 41% as already seen in figure 5). In Greece alone, the negative figure exceeds 50% of those surveyed, while in France there is also a negative attitude which is above the sample average. Spain and Cyprus are right on the sample average.

Figure 12 – Perception of presence of banquettes by country

The negative attitude of beachgoers towards the presence of banquettes should be assessed in light of the possible impact that the management of these banquettes could have on beach frequentation and consequently, on the tourist industry.

Figure 13 shows the aggregate data of the evaluation of the presence of the banquettes as a choice factor: note how the negative percentage is very close to the one relating to attitude in figure 7.

This figure is of considerable importance because it puts us in front of the fact that a negative attitude towards beaches with banquettes has direct economic repercussions on the tourism sector. This should not be overlooked by those responsible for managing these beaches.

It is interesting to note that 2% of the people who declared themselves indifferent would still choose the beach without banquettes if they had the possibility to do so.

Figure 13 – Presence of banquettes as a choice factor

The data on the presence of banquettes as a negative factor of choice, disaggregated by country and focused on the tourist component of the sample, offers us some interesting insights.

First of all, in absolute terms (figure 14) Italy and Spain show the greatest "tolerance" towards the presence of banquettes, while at the opposite end we find Greece, separated from France by only a small percentage.

Figure 14 – Presence of banquettes as a negative choice factor by country – beachgoers whole sample

However, the composition of these numbers is very different when comparing the points of view of tourists and residents. Figure 15 focuses on tourists and highlights the percentage of tourists interviewed in each country who are negatively influenced by the presence of Posidonia banquettes when choosing a beach.

Please note that the value of Greece in figure 15 is higher than the aggregate value of Greece itself in figure 14. The significance of this difference is that the high value of "intolerance" towards the presence of banquettes in Greece is determined, in proportion, by the negative attitude of the tourists rather than that of the local populations. Exactly the opposite happens in France, but with even greater distances between the data. It should be noted that the figure recorded in France refers to the beginning of the season. Therefore, it may be influenced by a greater desire for "naturalness" by tourists in that period who are looking for less crowded beaches. The pie chart shows the aggregate data related to the negative choice, between residents and tourists. In general, and despite the significant exception of Greece, tourists are more tolerant of the presence of banquettes, compared to the resident populations.

The analysis of these data helps us understand the potential impact of beach management policies, in relation to the preferences expressed by tourists.

Figure 15 – Presence of banquettes as a negative choice factor among tourists by country

Figure 16 shows us a very interesting fact: even in the presence of more than a 40% negative attitude of the sample regarding the presence of Posidonia banquettes on the beaches, only 10% of the people surveyed opt for the most drastic solution of total removal throughout the whole year. Another 28% ask for total removal only in summer. Specifically, even with a 41% negative attitude by the users of the sampled beaches, only 38% ask for total removal and disposal at least during the summer.

On the other hand, only 18% of the sample ask that the banquettes never be removed, compared to a 26% in figure 7 who still show a positive attitude towards them. There is no contradiction in the data, because in the histogram in Figure 7 (which also takes into account the intermediate positions), we note that those who have a positive attitude without reservations amount to about 16%.

Figure 16 – In which way banquettes should be managed?

The tables below show the interviewees' attitudes towards the advantages and disadvantages of beached Posidonia.

Table 1

Seagrass banquettes advantages (From 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree)	Average	St. dev.
If removed, it can be used as a raw material	4,0	1,2
It protects the beach from erosion	3,9	1,2
It's an ecosystem important for biodiversity	3,9	1,3
It's a good place to enjoy the beach	2,1	1,3

The advantages listed have been identified starting from the main ecosystem services offered by the banquettes, while the disadvantages are identified as disturbing factors with respect to the use of the beach for recreational purposes. Surprisingly enough, the advantage which is the most perceived is that of the use of Posidonia as a raw material, but just as well perceived are the function of protecting the beach from erosion and that of being an important factor for biodiversity. Note that the answers in addition to having obtained the highest score also have the least variability.

The popularity of Posidonia in relation to the use of the beach for recreational purposes is decidedly low.

Table 2

Seagrass banquettes disadvantages (From 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree)	Average	St. dev.
It emanates an unpleasant smell	3,1	1,5
It makes unpleasant / difficult bathing or swimming in the proximity	3,2	1,5
Bothersome animals live in the banquette	2,6	1,5
The leaves often stick to the body	3,4	1,5
It accumulate debris	3,3	1,5

The evaluation of the disadvantages appears more homogeneous but less clear, both in terms of the value of the evaluation and in terms of variability of the answers.

The only relevant fact is that the presence of annoying animals in the banquettes is actually quite well tolerated, having obtained the lowest score.

In relation to the various initiatives that could be activated to increase awareness and acceptance of seagrass banquettes, 74% of respondents said they favored the use of specific green labels (figure 17) for information and promotion, which would be assigned to the beaches in a natural state, i.e. with the possible presence of banquettes.

Figure 17 – Green label as a factor to increase acceptance of banquettes

This data is interesting because it shows a high degree of trust in the green label as a tool. As we will probably see in figure 21, this is in relation to the rather low level of public information on the management of seagrass banquettes and their role in protecting beaches and dunes from erosion, as well as being an indicator of good sea health.

2.2.3 EVALUATION SECTION

The analysis carried out to evaluate the economic benefits derived from the presence of banquettes on the beach led to a questionnaire given to beachgoers to estimate the WTP.

The first purpose is to establish the payment principle (Bateman and Langford, 1997). Therefore, the respondents were asked whether they agreed or disagreed with the principle of paying an extra fee to keep the banquettes on the beach.

The main purpose of this application is to validate the refusal and give it meaning in order to avoid making the respondents uncomfortable about declaring a zero amount or offending them with the presumption that in any case a positive WTP is expected from them.

The main interest for economic analysis consists in the values expressed by a willingness to pay, which allowed for the simulation of a demand curve for the use of beaches in a natural state, without any removal of the banquettes.

Another data of great interest emerging from the analysis concerns the motivations of the non-willing respondents (figure 18).

Figure 18 – Willingness to pay to keep the beach in a natural state, by keeping the banquette on

Although the interview was conducted without highlighting the idea of giving a role to the public administration, the relative majority indicates as their motivation the fact that since environmental goods are a public asset, management and related expenses should fall on local administrations. This answer denotes a reflex which is hard to extinguish in public users of non-market goods.

A and D are the only responses that denote a real aversion to the presence of banquettes or to the concept of a natural beach. As is shown, this is 13% of the non-willing respondents which is equal to 7.7% of the entire sample.

BENEFIT-COST ANALISYS

Benefit

In order to attribute an economic value to the seagrass banquettes, intended as an environmental good, it is necessary to refer to the ecosystem services they provide, and consequently to investigate the economic value of the service, rather than of the good itself.

With this criterion, the survey was given to users of the chosen beaches, to know how much an individual would be willing to pay in order to enjoy a beach in its natural state for recreational purposes, without having the banquettes removed.

As a result, a compensated demand was obtained for the use of the sample beaches maintained in a natural state, with the seagrass banquettes.

Figure 19 – WTP for beaches with seagrass banquettes: compensated demand

The rather flat trend of the curve tells us that it appears inelastic with respect to the price. This is like saying that the price changes have little influence (the prices requested in the sample ranged from €1 to the maximum value of €350), so the real difference is between the 41% who are willing to pay and the 59% who are not.

As seen in the methods section, the calculation of the area below the demand curve expresses the WTP of the sample.

$$\int_1^{115} (-16,91\ln(x) + 121) dx = 6.494,51$$

Note, however, that the value $R^2 = 0,0728$ in figure 19 is too low for us to be able to rely on the demand curve constructed by means of logarithmic interpolation.

We must therefore resort to the method based on the discrete values (table 3), obtained from the sum of the areas of the rectangles obtained by multiplying each price class by the number of responses that express it.

Table 3

amount	people	WTP
- €	715	- €
1,00 €	3	3,00 €
2,00 €	4	8,00 €
3,00 €	1	3,00 €
5,00 €	103	515,00 €
10,00 €	115	1.150,00 €
15,00 €	1	15,00 €
20,00 €	108	2.160,00 €
25,00 €	1	25,00 €
30,00 €	1	30,00 €
40,00 €	42	1.680,00 €
50,00 €	11	550,00 €
60,00 €	20	1.200,00 €
80,00 €	4	320,00 €
100,00 €	39	3.900,00 €
120,00 €	4	480,00 €
140,00 €	3	420,00 €
200,00 €	9	1.800,00 €
240,00 €	1	240,00 €
300,00 €	3	900,00 €
350,00 €	2	700,00 €
sample WTP		16.099,00 €

The value obtained, equal to €16.099,00 can be projected onto the entire population using the conversion factor.

As explained in the methodological section, the population has been calculated on the basis of the carrying capacity of the beaches, in order to compare in a homogeneous way the costs and benefits in conditions of full employment of the beach as a resource.

Table 4

	total	willing	not willing
Sample	1.190	475	715
Population	593.669	236.968	356.700
Conversion factor	498,88	498,88	498,88

Table 5

Sample WTP	€16.099,00
Population WTP	€8.031.496,59
Economic benefit per m²	€2,08

The final result tells us that the potential demand for keeping these beaches natural translates to a willingness to pay up to €8.031.496,59. This amounts to €2.08 per square meter of surface for the sampled beaches if they are kept in a natural state without removing the banquettes.

Cost

The WTP based approach as a basis for assessing the benefits generated by the banquettes as an integral part of a beach in natural conditions leads us to evaluate the cost determined by the presence of the banquettes. This is in relation to the use of the beach for recreational purposes.

In the previous analyses we examined the presence of the banquettes on the beach as a choice factor (based on the 2P question contained in the questionnaire and elaborated in figure 13), and discovered that 43% of the sample excludes the beach from their choices if "cluttered" by the presence of the banquettes.

A loss of tourists can be considered a good indicator of the costs associated with the presence of banquettes, or with the management's decision not to remove

them, with reference to the use of the recreational service of the beaches. On the contrary, resignation by the resident population cannot be considered a cost, if we adopt the simplified hypothesis that local consumption simply takes other forms but does not vary in amounts.

Let's remember that in figure 15 the percentage of tourists in the sample, declaring the presence of banquettes as a negative factor of choice, amounts to 44%.

In order to assess the damage resulting from the loss of tourists, a reliable indicator of the average daily tourist expense, net of travel costs, was sought in the bibliography. This estimate was elaborated in relation to the expenses of tourists of various international origins in Italy in 2012, and inflated to the exchange value of the Euro in 2018.

On the basis of the main tourist flow of 2012, we consider an average daily per capita expenditure of €101,42 (Source: our processing on Banca d'Italia data). Therefore, regarding the potential demand in conditions of maximum capacity on the beaches in our survey, the economic loss due to the presence of banquettes is obtained in the following way. First, we take the number of beachgoers and calculate in the 43% of them who consider the presence of banquettes a negative factor of choice. Once we have obtained this value, we must calculate the share of tourists, which amounts to 44%. This value must then be multiplied by the tourist's average daily expenditure, to obtain the final result of the loss due to the presence of the banquettes in the unit of time.

In summary:

Table 6

Per capita daily spending	€	101,42
Tourists loss		112.067,63
Total economic loss	€	11.365.899,54
Economic loss per m²	€	2,95

Final considerations

From the elaborations made, the management's decision to keep the beaches in a natural state has a negative economic impact on the tourism industry, equal to about €3 per m². Meanwhile, the estimated positive impact would amount to about €2 per m², obtained by the quota of beachgoers who express a demand for naturalness in the beaches frequented.

Ignoring criticisms of the CVM in general, as reported in the methodological section, the main consideration that emerges is that if you ask a group which is mostly using only one ecosystem service of the beach (recreation), and which has declared itself "poorly informed about the role of the banquettes in maintaining the balance of the beach", it is logical to expect that the benefits related to the presence of seagrass banquettes on the beach are going to be underestimated.

This information could not be provided before the interview because part of the interview was specifically aimed at assessing the degree of awareness of the beachgoers.

Other approaches could be used to partially fill the highlighted gaps. For example, the cost of removing and disposing of the banquettes as an opportunity cost of leaving the beach in a natural state could be considered. One could also calculate the loss of beach due to removal and erosion (Walker, 1982), in terms of the costs of nourishment to be undertaken. All of these methods, including the CVM already used, can highlight elements of the composition of the TEV, but perhaps only the CVM can take into account benefits deriving from the quantification of the value of non-use.

2.2.4 AWARENESS SECTION

The purpose of this section is to verify the degree of awareness of the sample of beachgoers surveyed.

Regarding the role of banquettes in preserving beaches and dunes from erosion, the general fact is that a large percentage of beachgoers (44%) is unaware of the role banquettes play in the formation and maintenance of beaches (figure 20).

Figure 20 – Awareness of role of banquettes in conservation of beaches and dunes

The disaggregated figure clearly indicates that more information is available to those surveyed on the Italian and Spanish beaches, while the other areas are much further behind.

This figure confirms and provides a reasonable interpretation for what has already been seen in figure 12: the places where the awareness of the banquettes' role in beach protection is greater, are the places where the greatest tolerance was shown towards its presence.

The data related to satisfaction on public information about banquettes (figure 21), tells us that, in general, there is a negative perception among beachgoers of the public administrations' effort to inform people about the usefulness of the banquettes.

Figure 21 – Satisfaction of beachgoers on the public information on the subject of seagrass banquettes

The disaggregated figure, although generally low, sees a resoundingly negative judgment in Greece. This is not surprising when we compare it to the results for the same country in figures 12, 14 and 15, relating to attitudes about the presence of seagrass banquettes on beaches and the consequent choice behavior.

3. STAKEHOLDER EXPECTATIONS SURVEY 3.4.2

3.1 METHODOLOGY

3.1.1 THE SURVEY

The survey on the stakeholders' expectations of the effects of seagrass banquette management consisted in verifying the general attitude of local administrators (LGA) and touristic operators (TOs), towards the presence of banquettes and its consequences on economic activities of the territory.

To this end, a special questionnaire was prepared containing a general part, a part dedicated to the LGAs and another one dedicated to the TOs.

The methodology involved the survey of a random sample of people at a number of tourist destinations in Italy, France, Greece, Cyprus, and Spain.

Each partner was asked to complete an "LGA" questionnaire for at least 20 coastal municipalities (if present in the region).

For each coastal municipality that responded positively, at least one in the "beach tourism" category and one in the "accommodation" category of the questionnaire had to be returned. If one of the two options was missing, partners were asked to submit two completed questionnaires for the remaining option.

Ultimately, each partner had to deliver the datasheet filled with at least 60 questionnaires: 20 LGA, 20 beach tourism and 20 accommodation.

Each partner was provided with a survey package that included three files:

- Expectations_survey_form_ISTRUCTIONS.docx (Annex 3)
- Expectations_survey_form_QUESTIONNAIRE.docx
- Expectations_survey_DATASHEET.xlsx

The questionnaire was divided into sections, relating to the subdivision of the data into topics, and to the subsequent statistical elaboration. One specific section was elaborated for LGAs, another for TOs.

In the subsequent tables, the final results of the locations sampled either for LGAs and for TOs are reported.

Table 8

Data collected by	Country_Region
IMC	Italy_Sardinia
EcoLogica	Italy_Continent
EID-Med	France
HCMR	Greece
IUCN	Cyprus
IUCN	Spain

3.1.2 THE SURVEY FORM

The GENERAL DATA section is NOT part of the survey and should be filled in before submitting the questionnaire, in order to be able to track it down and give it a location.

Questionnaires had to be submitted to two distinct categories of stakeholders:

1. Local Government Administrations (LGA)
2. Touristic operators (TO)

For the category "LGA" a public officer must be interviewed for each institution competent in the management of seagrass banquettes.

For the category "TO" one of the two available options must be selected:

- Beach tourism
- Accommodation

"Beach tourism" means activities based on the provision of bathing facilities, such as beach booths, equipment rental, bathing establishments, etc., as well as restaurants and bars, etc.

The part concerning the conservation level in the area is designed to check the legislative level of conservation. Note that for LGA we wanted to know which levels of conservation are applied in the territory of the municipality. To this aim, it was possible to tick more than one box, if different levels of conservation co-exist.

For the TOs, located in a specific place, the first option is an alternative to the other two, which can coexist. For example, if "National/regional ordinary legislation" is ticked, it is understood that this is not an MPA nor a Natura 2000 site. In contrast, an MPA can also be a Natura 2000 site.

GENERAL DATA

Partner _____

Survey form No. ____

Date ____/____/____

Typology:

Local Government Administrations (LGA)

Touristic operator

a) Beach tourism

b) Accommodation

Conservation level over the area:

National/regional ordinary legislation

Marine or Coastal Protected Area

Natura 2000 site

Place of survey: _____

Municipality: _____

Region (Administrative district): _____

Country: _____

The GENERAL SECTION aimed to investigate the overall attitude of stakeholders towards the seagrass banquettes. Question 2 in particular was designed to establish a hierarchy among the main reasons for dissatisfaction with the management of seagrass banquettes in the area.

GENERAL SECTION

- 1) Are you satisfied of the current management on seagrass banquettes along your area?
- YES
- NO

If answer is YES, skip to question 3

If answer is NO:

- 2) In your opinion, what do you think are the main weaknesses (rating from 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree)
- a. Administrative and bureaucratic procedure needed to remove banquettes – rating _____
 - b. Waste Management – rating _____
 - c. Current rules are too addressed towards protection – rating _____
 - d. Current rules do not take into account the different beach typologies and features – rating _____
- 3) How do you evaluate the presence of seagrass banquettes in relation to their influence on tourist on the beaches in your site?

Negatively		Indifferent		Positively
1	2	3	4	5

The LGA section was conceived to obtain two different types of information: to discover the banquette management policies employed by the local administrations, and to verify their perceptions of the presence of the banquettes, their management and on the effects on tourism, in relation to the expectations of the operators of the tourism sector and of the tourists themselves.

SECTION DEDICATED TO Local Government Administrations

1G) Does your institution/administration remove the banquettes?

- YES
- NO

2G) If answer is YES

A. In which way?

- i. Manually
- ii. Light machinery (sifting machines)
- iii. Heavy machinery (bulldozers)

B. Could you provide us with the quantity m³OR tons per year?

i. m³ _____

ii. tons _____

C. Could you provide us with the yearly management cost (euro):

- iv. removal operations _____
- v. disposal _____

D. How many beaches are managed by the institution/authority? _____

E. Number of beaches involved in removal operations _____

3G) If the answer is NO, why do you not remove the banquettes?

- a. High costs
- b. Bureaucratic and/or administrative reasons
- c. Environmental and/or ecological reasons

Other _____

4G) What are the main goals of your management strategy on banquettes?

- a. In response to touristic demands
- b. In response to local residents demands
- c. In response to economic restraints
- d. Nature conservation

5G) Do you consider that the presence of banquettes affects the touristic activities in your area?

a. Positively why...

- i) It protects the beach from erosion
- ii) It gives an image of naturalness

Other _____

b. Negatively why ...

- i) It makes tourists unhappy, (uncomfortable, etc.)
- ii) Removal and disposal procedures are difficult and expensive
- iii) Helps to accumulate debris

Other _____

6G) Do you think that the institution of a specific green label for natural beaches (with a criteria for good management or no banquettes removal) may help to increase tourists' awareness and acceptance of Posidonia banquettes?

YES

NO

7G) Before this interview, did you ever consider that seagrass such as Posidonia banquettes can be useful for the conservation of beaches and dunes?

YES

NO

8G) Do you think that public information about the ecological role that seagrass banquettes have on beaches/dunes is sufficient?

YES

NO

Like the LGA section, the TO section was designed to meet the expectations of touristic operators regarding the management policies of local administrators regarding the banquettes, as well as the effects of the presence of seagrass banquettes on tourism .

SECTION DEDICATED TO TOURISTIC OPERATORS

1T) In which way do you think the banquette should be managed?

- a) Total removal and disposal for the whole year
- b) Total removal and disposal only in summer season
- c) Temporary removal and repositioning at the end of summer season
- d) Partial removal to avoid excessive accumulations
- e) No removal at all

2T) Do you consider that the presence of seagrass banquettes affects your economic activity?

a. Positively why ...

- i) It protects the beach from erosion
- ii) It gives an image of naturalness

Other _____

b. Negatively why ...

- i) It makes tourists unhappy
- ii) Removal and disposal procedures are difficult and expensive
- iii) Helps to accumulate debris

Other _____

3T) Do you think that the institution of a specific green label for natural beaches (with a criteria for good management or no banquettes removal) may help to increase tourists' awareness and acceptance of Posidonia banquettes?

- YES
- NO

4T) Before this interview, did you ever consider that seagrass such as Posidonia banquettes can be useful for the conservation of beaches and dunes?

- YES
- NO

5T) Do you think that public information about the ecological role that seagrass banquettes have on beaches/dunes is sufficient?

- YES
- NO

3.2 RESULTS 3.4.2

3.2.1 GENERAL SECTION

This section focuses on the attitude of public and private operators regarding the management of banquettes.

Naturally, the public operators respond with reference to the rules and regulations that dictates their management activities, so the answer is mainly addressed to the legislator.

Private operators responded by expressing their level of satisfaction in relation to the impact of local policies, and therefore the laws that regulate them and their businesses, influenced by the influx and satisfaction of tourists.

Figure 22 shows that, in general, both public and private operators expressed satisfaction with management methods. However, in the private sector the gap between the satisfied and the dissatisfied was less than that of the public sector.

The largest share of dissatisfied TOs was influenced by the particular case of Sardinia, in which there was found to be an inverse relationship between levels of satisfaction of LGAs (70%) and TOs (33%). This gap can be explained by the management policies adopted by the Sardinian government, which are too conservative in the opinion of the TOs.

Figure 22 – Satisfaction level of the current management of seagrass banquettes

Particular attention must be paid to the fact that, as shown in tables 9 and 10, among the causes of dissatisfaction, economic operators blame bureaucracy,

thus addressing mainly the local administrations. On the other hand, the LGA absolve their own bureaucratic rules, while accusing the legislation of leaning too far towards protection.

Table 9

TO: main weaknesses in current management of segrass banquette (From 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree)	Average	St. dev.
a. Administrative and bureaucratic procedure needed to remove banquettes	3,79	1,66
b. Waste Management	3,26	1,59
c. Current rules are too addressed towards protection	3,14	1,50
d. Current rules do not take into account the different beach typologies and features	3,59	1,43

Table 7

LGA: main weaknesses in current management of segrass banquette (From 1 totally disagree to 5 totally agree)	Average	St. dev.
a. Administrative and bureaucratic procedure needed to remove banquettes	2,84	1,61
b. Waste Management	3,03	1,58
c. Current rules are too addressed towards protection	3,28	1,65
d. Current rules do not take into account the different beach typologies and features	3,22	1,60

39% of the answers that do not disagree with question **c.** are from LGA in Natura 2000 sites or MPAs

With reference to the influence of the presence of banquettes on tourists (figure 23), public and private operators have practically overlapping positions. For the overall negative perception in equal measure, public operators express less drastic positions, while the totally negative evaluation prevails in touristic operators.

Figure 23 – Perception of the presence of banquettes in relation to their influence on tourists

3.2.2 SECTION DEDICATED TO LOCAL GOVERNMENT ADMINISTRATIONS

This section had a rather unsatisfactory level of responses to the questionnaire, in relation to the generally uncooperative behaviour of some local administrations.

As a result, the number of answers not given or given only partially is high, and therefore should not be used for statistical processing.

As shown in figure 24, 79% of the sampled LGAs routinely remove the banquettes.

Figure 24 – Local Administrations that usually remove the banquettes

The main means of removal (figure 25) consists of heavy machinery (45%), while the manual removal, at only 16%, is remarkably much less common.

Figure 25 – Methods mainly used for removal

On average, the local administrations interviewed manage 8 beaches, on half of which the banquettes are removed. The data has a significant variance.

The LGAs that leave the banquettes do it mostly (58%) for environmental reasons, while the administrative management and the costs of the procedure do not appear to significantly affect the decision (figure 26).

Figure 26 – Reasons why the LGA does not remove the banquettes

The main driving factors of the management policies (figure 27), declared by the LGAs, are the conservation of nature and, in a preponderant measure, the requests of tourists.

In fact, the LGA do not have a direct channel of communication with tourists, so we can reasonably assume that their main source of information about the tourists' orientations comes from companies in the sector (TOs). During the discussion and comparison between the results of the two surveys, we will also analyze how the perceptions of one and the expectations of the other coincide in reality.

Figure 27 – Drivers of LGA management strategies on banquettes

In the survey, all the interviewees were asked three key questions: one (figure 28) concerns the validity of green labels as a tool to increase awareness and acceptance of the banquettes and their role in the environment.

Another question was intended to assess the interviewees' awareness (figure 29) and the last one was focused on the evaluation of the level of satisfaction with the public information present on the topic (figure 30).

Figure 28 – LGA: Green labels as a factor to increase acceptance of banquettes

Figure 29 – LGA: Awareness of the role of banquettes in conservation of beaches and dunes

Figure 30 – LGA: Is public information sufficient?

As a result, it emerges above all that a good part of the operators in the public sector still has some confidence (about 60%) in the green labels as a tool for creating awareness and acceptance of the banquettes.

The operators declared to a large extent to be aware of the essential role of the banquettes in beach equilibrium. They complained about insufficient public information, suggesting that this role should be carried out by public bodies other than the local administrations.

3.2.3 SECTION DEDICATED TO TOURISTIC OPERATORS

From the general data of the questionnaire, it emerges in figure 31 that the sample of touristic operators is composed of 35% in the "accommodation" category with the remaining part in the "beach tourism" category.

Figure 31 – Sample composition of the touristic operators

Figure 32 shows the composition of the sample from the point of view of the conservation level: 53% is regulated by the ordinary legislation, while the remaining 47% falls into protected marine or coastal areas, or in Natura 2000 sites or both.

Figure 32 – Touristic operators: conservation level of the sampled area

Figure 33 clearly shows a notable inflexibility of touristic operators regarding ways of managing banquettes. In fact, 19% ask for removal all year round, while as many as 49% ask for removal and disposal only in summer. In total, 65% of touristic operators surveyed ask for the most drastic management form at least in the summer.

Figure 33 – Touristic operators: in which way should the banquettes be managed?

The methods of banquette management requested by touristic operators are best explained in figure 34, which shows that the perceived negative aspects of the presence of banquettes on the beach clearly outweigh the positive aspects. Among these "accusations", the main one concerns not the cost, nor the accumulation of other debris of non-natural origin, but the fact that it makes tourists unhappy.

Figure 34 – How the presence of banquettes affects the touristic activities

In spite of those who claim to be perfectly aware of the function of the banquettes in beach equilibrium (figure 35), there are few who indicate among the advantages the fact that the banquettes protect the beach from erosion. Even fewer see the "naturalness" of the beach as a positive factor for attracting tourists.

Figure 35 – Touristic operators: awareness of the role of banquettes in conservation of beaches and dunes

As we can see in figure 36, with regard to territorial marketing policies, operators have a rather low level of confidence in the effectiveness of the green labels as a factor for improving the acceptance of banquettes by tourists.

Figure 36 – Touristic operators: green labels as a factor for increasing acceptance of banquettes

Figure 37 shows the data on the satisfaction of touristic operators with the level of public information on banquettes. This information regards how the banquettes are formed and the fact that they are an indicator of good seawater quality and an essential element for the balance of the beach.

Even in this case, a remarkably negative attitude prevails, providing us with the following question: if the public information on the banquettes were adequate, would it improve banquette acceptance by the touristic operators?

Figure 37 – Touristic operators: is public information sufficient?

4. CONCLUSIONS

Final considerations on the comparative analysis of the two surveys

The research highlighted some interesting results, both regarding the perception of beachgoers and regarding the perception and expectations of public and private operators.

In general, there is a substantially negative attitude towards the presence of seagrass banquettes on the beaches. However, the beachgoers had a more articulated approach, compared to the operators, both public and private.

Figure 11, along with all the responses concerning public information, unequivocally shows that there is a strong link between the acceptance of banquettes by tourists, their level of education and the information available about banquettes and their role as a stabilizing factor for beaches.

On the other hand, the other responses from tourists and the operators themselves suggest that marketing aimed at attracting tourists to immaculate, tropical beaches is a negative factor for the acceptance of the presence of banquettes. The survey was not structured to study this aspect specifically, but a look at the data disaggregated by nation, suggests that some particularly negative peaks (especially in the responses of tourists) are related to the strategic positioning of coastal tourism systems and their consequent advertising proposals.

In figure 38, the comparison between the perception of the presence of banquettes between beachgoers and operators of local administrations and tourism companies, shows a particularly interesting situation that we will see repeated in other analyses:

1. The peaks of negative ratings are much higher in operators than users, while the positive ratings are much higher among beachgoers.
2. The evaluations of local touristic operators and those of local administrations coincide.

Figure 38 – Comparison between different perceptions of the presence of banquettes between operators and beachgoers

The consequences of what is shown in figure 38 are found in figure 39: touristic operators and local administrations overestimate the negative impact of banquettes on tourism to the same proportions. This is evident when compared to the perception of beachgoers. Even more macroscopic is the figure representing the indifference of beachgoers to the presence of banquettes that is clearly superior to what was expected by public and private operators.

It is true that the banquettes have a negative impact on tourism, as evidenced in figures 13 and 14, but the proportions of the phenomenon appear less dramatic than expected by public and private operators. This is especially due to the excessive underestimation of the tourists' indifference to the presence of the banquettes.

Figure 39 – Does the presence of seagrass banquettes have an impact on tourism?

If we focus on the high level of coincidence of the responses of local administrations with those of the touristic operators, we can assume that local administrators base their own considerations on the information received from the entrepreneurs, rather than on direct contact with the tourists. The entrepreneurs’ concerns about losing even one tourist due to the presence of the banquettes leads to a substantial overstatement of the problem. This makes the professional figure of the touristic operator unable to accept management policies other than removal.

Figures 16 and 33 analyzed the expectations of beachgoers and touristic operators about the type of banquette management that local administrations should implement. The comparison between the different evaluations done in figure 40 once again shows the much more moderate position of the beachgoers than the touristic operators.

Figure 40 – Comparison between the different expectations of touristic operators and beachgoers about banquette management

All the subjects involved in the two surveys agreed that the information available on the relationship between the banquettes and the state of the sea and the beach equilibrium is insufficient. The beachgoers showed more trust in the green label as a tool when compared to the LGA operators and, to a lesser degree, to the TOs.

Highlights

Beach management policies of local administrations are mainly influenced by their perception of tourists' requests.

LGAs do not have direct contact with tourists, but rather rely on the perception of TOs.

The tourists' acceptance of the banquettes on the beaches is superior to what the TOs expect.

The tourists' acceptance of the banquettes on the beaches increases as their awareness and the amount of available information increases.

Public information policies are universally perceived as insufficient.

The presence of banquettes on the beaches is a negative factor of choice for a significant portion of tourists. This is particularly true for the localities that base their marketing on the offer of white beaches of the tropical model.

The analysis of the benefits and costs of the presence of the banquettes in relation to the loss of tourists tells us that there is an economic loss directly linked to the presence of the banquettes. However, this calculation does not take into account the possible damage resulting from erosion due to banquette removal, either in terms of a loss of tourists, or in terms of subsequent restoration costs.

Tips for possible developments

The analysis carried out provides some fundamental information for developing a strategy to increase the acceptance by tourists and touristic operators of the presence of banquettes on Mediterranean beaches.

The key factor is certainly cultural and it has been shown how important information is. Therefore, it would be crucial to relate the information and sensitization policies on banquettes (implemented by the public sector) with both the public tourism marketing policies and with those of private companies. This analysis should be conducted both in quantitative terms, with respect to the investment in communication, and in terms of quality compared to the contents of the message.

A more complete assessment of the economic implications of the management of banquettes would be needed. For this purpose, the real erosive effects on a significant sample of Mediterranean coasts subjected to the removal of the banquettes should be evaluated, in order to relate the phenomenon to the economic effects due to the loss of beaches and sand dunes.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 - STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTION: LOCATIONS OF THE SURVEY ON BEACHGOERS

Place of survey	Municipality	Region (Administrative district)	Country
Lido di Alghero	Alghero	Sardinia	Italy
Calette delle Bombarde	Alghero	Sardinia	Italy
Arborea	Arborea	Sardinia	Italy
San Giovanni di Sinis	Cabras	Sardinia	Italy
Is Aruttas	Cabras	Sardinia	Italy
Sa Mesa Longa	Cabras	Sardinia	Italy
Maimoni	Cabras	Sardinia	Italy
Heraclea	Policoro	Basilicata	Italy
Baia di Trentova	Agropoli	Campania	Italy
Acciaroli	Salerno	Campania	Italy
Arenzano	Genova	Liguria	Italy
Torre Quetta	Bari	Puglia	Italy
Torre a Mare	Bari	Puglia	Italy
S. Spirito	Bari	Puglia	Italy
Pane e Pomodoro	Bari	Puglia	Italy
Spiaggia Verde	Barletta	Puglia	Italy
Torre Guaceto	Brindisi	Puglia	Italy
Torre S. Sabina	Carovigno	Puglia	Italy
Torre Guaceto	Carovigno	Puglia	Italy
Parco delle Dune Costiere	Fasano	Puglia	Italy
Archeolido	Fasano	Puglia	Italy
Punta Pizzo	Gallipoli	Puglia	Italy
Cala Spiriticchio	Giovinazzo	Puglia	Italy
Cesine	Lecce	Puglia	Italy

Spiaggia Libera	Lizzano	Puglia	Italy
Siponto	Manfredonia	Puglia	Italy
Porto	Mola Di Bari	Puglia	Italy
Torre Calderina	Molfetta	Puglia	Italy
Porto Ghiacciolo	Monopoli	Puglia	Italy
Cala Colonia	Monopoli	Puglia	Italy
Lido Sabbia D'oro	Monopoli	Puglia	Italy
Porto Ghiacciolo	Monopoli	Puglia	Italy
Lido Morelli	Ostuni	Puglia	Italy
Pilone	Ostuni	Puglia	Italy
Rosa Marina	Ostuni	Puglia	Italy
Diana Marina	Ostuni	Puglia	Italy
Macchia Mediterranea	Ostuni	Puglia	Italy
Alimini	Otranto	Puglia	Italy
San Vito	Polignano a Mare	Puglia	Italy
Torre Lapillo	Porto Cesareo	Puglia	Italy
Spiaggia di Levante	Rodi Garganico	Puglia	Italy
Marina di Pescoluse	Salve	Puglia	Italy
Monastero	Trani	Puglia	Italy
Torre S.Giovanni	Ugento	Puglia	Italy
Marina di Ugento	Ugento	Puglia	Italy
Pugnochiuso	Vieste	Puglia	Italy
San Teodoro	Marsala	Sicilia	Italy
Capo Feto	Mazara Del Vallo	Sicilia	Italy
Vendicari	Noto	Sicilia	Italy
San Giuliano	Trapani	Sicilia	Italy
Spiaggia delle Alghe	Cavo	Toscana	Italy
Marina di Pietrasanta	Pietrasanta	Toscana	Italy
La Conchiglia	San Vincenzo	Toscana	Italy
Faviere	Bormes Les Mimosas	Paca	France
Péno	Carqueiranne	Paca	France
Tombolo de Giens	Hyeres Les Palmiers	Paca	France

Almanarre	Hyeres Les Palmiers	Paca	France
Tombolo Ouest	Hyeres Les Palmiers	Paca	France
Miramar	La Londe Les Maures	Paca	France
Les Sablettes	La Seyne sur Mer	Paca	France
L'Aiguebelle	Le Lavandou	Paca	France
Pampelone	Saint Tropez	Paca	France
Les Cannebiers	Saint Tropez	Paca	France
Portissol	Sanary sur Mer	Paca	France
Plage Dorée	Sanary sur Mer	Paca	France
Lido	Sanary sur Mer	Paca	France
Tamaris	Sausset Les Pins	Paca	France
Baumettes	Sausset Les Pins	Paca	France
Petit Nid	Sausset Les Pins	Paca	France
Skalakia Beach, Anavissos	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Mavro Lithari Beach	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Saronida Beach	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Mavro Lithari Beach	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Ag. Dimitrios	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Livrochio Beach	Sithonia	Chalkidiki	Greece
Salonikios Beach	Sithonia	Chalkidiki	Greece
Gerakini Beach	Sithonia	Chalkidiki	Greece
Dimotiki Beach	Chios	Chios	Greece
Ag. Georgios	Hersonissos	Crete	Greece
Panepistimio	Mytilene	Lesvos	Greece
Makronissos	Ayia Napa	Famagusta	Cyprus
Konnos	Ayia Napa / Paralimni	Famagusta	Cyprus
Ayia Thekla	Sotira	Famagusta	Cyprus
Mackenzie	Larnaca	Larnaca	Cyprus
Psarolimano	Larnaca	Larnaca	Cyprus
Fontana Amorosa	Neo Chorio	Paphos	Cyprus

Geroskipou	Paphos	Paphos	Cyprus
Latsi	Polis Chrysochous	Paphos	Cyprus
El Pinet	Santa Pola	Alicante	Spain
Es Trenc	Campos	Islas Baleares	Spain
Espalmador	Sant Francesc	Islas Baleares	Spain
Es Carbo	Ses Salines	Islas Baleares	Spain

ANNEX 2 - PERCEPTION SURVEY FORM

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COMPLETING THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Each partner will have to complete at least 200 questionnaires in at least 4 different beaches localized in different municipalities. The beaches **MUST** be subjected, at least periodically, to banquettes deposition. Preferably, select at least 2 beaches with and 2 w/out banquette removal.

The questionnaire must be completed in all its parts to be considered valid.

GENERAL DATA

The master section is **NOT** part of the survey and must be filled in preliminarily by the person who submits the questionnaire.

In the "Partners" field, enter the name of the partner of the POSBEMED project that conducted the survey.

Fill in the appropriate fields.

Conservation level over the area

This question tends to check the legislative level of conservation. Note that the first option is alternative to the other two, which can coexist. So, if you choose "National/regional ordinary legislation" it is understood that it is not an MPA nor a Natura 2000 site. In contrast, an MPA can also be a Natura 2000 site.

To complete the section, complete the fields for the place of survey, municipality, administrative district and country.

In the field "Place of survey" please indicate the name of the beach (all lowercase).

Introduction

Explain briefly the objectives of the questionnaire and what is meant by Posidonia banquettes.

GENERAL SECTION

Tick the appropriate boxes

In the question 5) if the answer is "other" please specify the country in English

PERCEPTION SECTION

- 1P) Tick the appropriate box from 1 (negative) to 5 (positive)
- 2P) Tick ONE of the three boxes
- 3P) Tick ONE of the boxes
- 4P) Answer by assigning a score to the sentences a, b, c, d from 1 totally disagree to 5 completely agree
- 5P) Answer by assigning a score to the sentences a, b, c, d, e from 1 totally disagree to 5 completely agree
- 6P) Tick ONE of the two boxes

VALUATION SECTION

The persons who administer the questionnaires must be trained if unexperienced of contingent valuations. In particular, it is important to stress the fact that this is a simulation to estimate the value given by the "consumer" of a natural good, to keep it in a state of naturalness.

The answerer may consider how much he/she would be willing to pay to keep the natural good, not considering an active role of the State in this.

- 1V) Tick the appropriate box, if the answer is "other" please round off to 50
- 2V) Tick ONLY ONE box

AWARENESS SECTION

- 1W) Tick ONE of the two boxes
- 2W) Tick ONE of the two boxes

ANNEX 3 - EXPECTATIONS SURVEY FORM

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COMPLETING THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Each partner will have to complete an "LGA" questionnaire for at least 30 coastal municipalities.

The questionnaire must be completed in all its parts to be considered valid.

For each coastal municipality that responds positively, at least one of the "Beach tourism" category and one of the "Accommodation" category of the questionnaire must be returned. If one of the two options is missing, submit at least two completed questionnaires for the remaining option.

Ultimately, each partner must deliver the datasheet of 90 questionnaires: 30 LGA, 30 Beach tourism and 30 Accommodation.

GENERAL DATA

The master section is NOT part of the survey and must be filled in preliminarily by the person who submits the questionnaire.

In the "Partners" field, enter the name of the partner of the POSBEMED project that conducted the survey.

Fill in the appropriate fields.

Typology:

Questionnaires should be submitted to 2 distinct stakeholder categories:

1. Local Government Administrations (LGA)
2. Touristic operators

You will only have to tick the box for one of the two options.

For the category "LGA" a public officer must be interviewed for each institution competent in the management of Posidonia banquettes.

For the category "Touristic operators" one of the two linked options must be selected:

- Beach tourism
- Accommodation

"Beach tourism" means activities based on the provision of bathing facilities, such as beach booths, equipment rental, bathing establishments, etc., and restaurants, bars, etc.

Conservation level over the area

This question tends to check the legislative level of conservation. Note that for LGA is intended to know which levels of conservation are applied in the territory of the municipality. So, it is possible to tick more boxes, if different levels of conservation co-exist.

On the other hand, for the touristic operators, being located in a specific place, the first option is alternative to the other two, which can coexist. So, if you choose "National/regional ordinary legislation" it is understood that it is not an MPA nor a Natura 2000 site. In contrast, an MPA can also be a Natura 2000 site.

To complete the section, fill in the fields for the location (place of survey), municipality, and administrative district.

Since in the same place of survey every beach has a different name, you are invited to use the name of the place of survey in a broader sense instead of the single spot. For instance, in Sardinia, on the beaches of the Sinis Peninsula, will be used the synthetic "sinis" (all lowercase).

The field "Place of survey" must be filled only if the interviewee is a touristic operator.

Introduction

Explain briefly the objectives of the questionnaire and what is meant by Posidonia banquettes.

GENERAL SECTION

- 1) Tick one of the two boxes

If the answer is YES skip to question 3

If the answer is NO:

- 2) Answer by assigning a score to the sentences a, b, c, d, from 1 totally disagree to 5 completely agree
- 3) Tick the appropriate box 1 to 5

SECTION DEDICATED TO *Local Government Administrations (LGA)*

- 1G) Tick one of the two boxes, if the answer is YES skip to question 3G
- 2G) A. tick ONLY one choice
B. fill ONLY one field, do not use decimals
C. fill BOTH fields, do not use decimals
D. fill the corresponding field
E. fill the corresponding field
- 3G) Tick only one box, otherwise fill the "other" box synthetically, striving to standardize the answers received.
- 4G) Tick only one box
- 5G) Once the answer is chosen between "a." and "b.", tick only one box, otherwise fill the "other" box synthetically, striving to standardize the answers received.
- 6G) Tick one of the two boxes
- 7G) Tick one of the two boxes
- 8G) Tick one of the two boxes

SECTION DEDICATED TO TOURISTIC OPERATORS

- 1T) Tick only one box
- 2T) Once the answer is chosen between "a." and "b.", tick only one box, otherwise fill the "other" box synthetically, striving to standardize the answers received.
- 3T) Tick one of the two boxes
- 4T) Tick one of the two boxes
- 5T) Tick one of the two boxes

ANNEX 4 - STAKEHOLDERS' EXPECTATIONS: LOCATIONS OF THE SURVEY ON LGA

Municipality	Region (Administrative District)	Country
Alghero	Sardinia	Italy
Arborea	Sardinia	Italy
Arzachena	Sardinia	Italy
Buggerru	Sardinia	Italy
Calasetta	Sardinia	Italy
Cuglieri	Sardinia	Italy
La Maddalena	Sardinia	Italy
Maracalagonis	Sardinia	Italy
Muravera	Sardinia	Italy
Narbolia	Sardinia	Italy
San Teodoro	Sardinia	Italy
San Vero Milis	Sardinia	Italy
Santa Teresa	Sardinia	Italy
Sant'anna Arresi	Sardinia	Italy
Sant'antioco	Sardinia	Italy
Terralba	Sardinia	Italy
Tortolì	Sardinia	Italy
Valledoria	Sardinia	Italy
Villaptzu	Sardinia	Italy
Villasimius	Sardinia	Italy
Rotondella	Basilicata	Italy
Grado	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	Italy
Ventotene	Lazio	Italy
Arenzano	Liguria	Italy
Bergeggi	Liguria	Italy
Bogliasco	Liguria	Italy
Ceriale	Liguria	Italy
Loano	Liguria	Italy
Portovenere	Liguria	Italy

Santo Stefano al Mare	Liguria	Italy
Gabicce Mare	Marche	Italy
Senigallia	Marche	Italy
Campomarino	Molise	Italy
Bari	Puglia	Italy
Melendugno	Puglia	Italy
Monopoli	Puglia	Italy
Campo nell'Elba	Toscana	Italy
Castiglione della Pescaia	Toscana	Italy
Montignoso	Toscana	Italy
San Vincenzo	Toscana	Italy
Eraclea	Veneto	Italy
Venezia	Veneto	Italy
Antibes	Paca	France
Beaulieu sur Mer	Paca	France
Cannes	Paca	France
Carqueraine	Paca	France
Cavalaire sur Mer	Paca	France
Eze	Paca	France
Frejus	Paca	France
Grimaud	Paca	France
Hyerres Les Palmiers	Paca	France
La Croix Valmer	Paca	France
La Seyne sur Mer	Paca	France
Le Lavandou	Paca	France
Le Pradet	Paca	France
Marseille	Paca	France
Roqueburne sur Argens	Paca	France
Saint Cyr sur Mer	Paca	France
Saint Mandrier sur Mer	Paca	France
Saint Tropez	Paca	France
Sainte Maxime	Paca	France

Sanary sur Mer	Paca	France
Sausset Les Pins	Paca	France
Villefranche sur Mer	Paca	France
Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Spata-Artemida	Attica	Greece
Tanagra	Central Greece	Greece
Kassandra	Central Macedonia	Greece
Sithonia	Central Macedonia	Greece
Kissamos	Crete	Greece
Siteia	Crete	Greece
Chios	North Aegean	Greece
Lesvos	North Aegean	Greece
Loutraki	Peloponnese	Greece
Sifnos	South Aegean	Greece
Limassol	Akrotiri	Cyprus
Larnaca	Alaminos	Cyprus
Famagusta	Ayia Napa	Cyprus
Larnaca	Ayios Theodoros	Cyprus
Limassol	British Sovereign Bases	Cyprus
Larnaca	Dromolaxia/Meneou	Cyprus
Pafos	Geroskipou	Cyprus
Nicosia	Kato Pyrgos	Cyprus
Pafos	Kissonerga	Cyprus
Pafos	Kouklia	Cyprus
Larnaca	Larnaca	Cyprus
Limassol	Moni	Cyprus
Pafos	Pafos	Cyprus
Famagusta	Paralimni	Cyprus
Limassol	Pentakomo	Cyprus
Larnaca	Pervolia	Cyprus
Larnaca	Pyla	Cyprus
Famagusta	Sotira	Cyprus
Larnaca	Voroklini	Cyprus

Larnaca	Zygi	Cyprus
Benidorm	Alicante	Spain
Benissa	Alicante	Spain
Benitachell	Alicante	Spain
Calpe	Alicante	Spain
El Campello	Alicante	Spain
Santa Pola	Alicante	Spain
Teulada	Alicante	Spain
Torrevieja	Alicante	Spain
Villajolosa	Alicante	Spain
Benicassim	Castellon	Spain
Torreblanca	Castellon	Spain
Alcudia	Islas Baleares	Spain
Andratx	Islas Baleares	Spain
Arta	Islas Baleares	Spain
Calvia	Islas Baleares	Spain
Campos	Islas Baleares	Spain
Capdepera	Islas Baleares	Spain
Ibiza	Islas Baleares	Spain
Llucmajor	Islas Baleares	Spain
Manacor	Islas Baleares	Spain
Muro	Islas Baleares	Spain
Pollensa	Islas Baleares	Spain
Sant Francesc	Islas Baleares	Spain
Sant Llorenç	Islas Baleares	Spain
Santa Margarita	Islas Baleares	Spain
Santany	Islas Baleares	Spain
Ses Salines	Islas Baleares	Spain
Son Servera	Islas Baleares	Spain
Daimuz	Valencia	Spain
Oliva	Valencia	Spain
Xeraco	Valencia	Spain

ANNEX 5 - STAKEHOLDERS' EXPECTATIONS: LOCATIONS OF THE SURVEY ON TO

Place of Survey	Municipality	Region (Administrative District)	Country
Lido di Alghero	Alghero	Sardinia	Italy
Arborea	Arborea	Sardinia	Italy
Cannigione	Arzachena	Sardinia	Italy
Cala dei Ginepri	Arzachena	Sardinia	Italy
Li Junchi	Badesi	Sardinia	Italy
Badesi	Badesi	Sardinia	Italy
Santa Maria Navarrese	Baunei	Sardinia	Italy
Marina di Budoni	Budoni	Sardinia	Italy
Buggerru	Buggerru	Sardinia	Italy
Calasetta	Calasetta	Sardinia	Italy
Is Arenas	Cuglieri	Sardinia	Italy
La Maddalena	La Maddalena	Sardinia	Italy
Caprera	La Maddalena	Sardinia	Italy
Torre delle Stelle	Maracalagonis	Sardinia	Italy
Costa Rei	Muravera	Sardinia	Italy
Muravera	Muravera	Sardinia	Italy
Is Arenas	Narbolia	Sardinia	Italy
San Teodoro	San Teodoro	Sardinia	Italy
Capo Coda Cavallo	San Teodoro	Sardinia	Italy
S'Anea Scoada	San Vero Milis	Sardinia	Italy
Santa Teresa	Santa Teresa	Sardinia	Italy
Rena Bianca	Santa Teresa	Sardinia	Italy
Porto Pino	Sant'anna Arresi	Sardinia	Italy
Maladroxia	Sant'Antioco	Sardinia	Italy
La Pelosa	Stintino	Sardinia	Italy
Marceddi	Terralba	Sardinia	Italy
Fox Lioni	Tortolì	Sardinia	Italy

Tortolì	Tortolì	Sardinia	Italy
Valledoria	Valledoria	Sardinia	Italy
Porto Corallo	Villaputzu	Sardinia	Italy
Villasimius	Villasimius	Sardinia	Italy
Bergeggi	Bergeggi	Liguria	Italy
Bagni Playa de Luna	Bergeggi	Liguria	Italy
Isola di Pianosa	Campo nell'Elba	Toscana	Italy
Marina di Campo	Campo nell'Elba	Toscana	Italy
Isola d'Elba	Campo nell'Elba	Toscana	Italy
Baia di Marina di Campo	Campo nell'Elba	Toscana	Italy
West Coast	Ceriale	Liguria	Italy
Coast	Loano	Liguria	Italy
Beach	Loano	Liguria	Italy
Bagni Kursaal	Loano	Liguria	Italy
Cinquale	Montignoso	Toscana	Italy
Beach	San Vincenzo	Toscana	Italy
San Vincenzo	San Vincenzo	Toscana	Italy
Peno	Carqueiranne	Paca	France
Almanarre	Hyerès Les Palmiers	Paca	France
Tamaris	La Londe Les Maures	Paca	France
Sablettes	La Seyne sur Mer	Paca	France
Esplanade	Sanary sur Mer	Paca	France
Bonnegrace	Six Fours Les Plages	Paca	France
Limenas	Hersonissos	Crete	Greece
Anissaras	Hersonissos	Crete	Greece
Creta Maris, Crete	Hersonissos	Crete	Greece
Aldemar, Crete	Hersonissos	Crete	Greece
Ag. Georgios	Kerkyra	Ionian Islands	Greece
Gourniatis	Kos	South Aegean	Greece
Gerakini, Halkidiki	Polygyros	Central Macedonia	Greece

Kalyves, Halkidiki	Polygyros	Central Macedonia	Greece
Lagonisi	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Mavro Lithari	Saronikos	Attica	Greece
Livrohio, Halkidiki	Sithonia	Central Macedonia	Greece
Armenistis	Sithonia	Central Macedonia	Greece
Konnos	Ayia Napa / Paralimni	Famagusta	Cyprus
Mackenzie	Larnaca	Larnaca	Cyprus
Psarolimano	Larnaca	Larnaca	Cyprus
Fontana Amorosa	Neo Chorio	Paphos	Cyprus
Geroskipou	Paphos	Paphos	Cyprus
Latsi	Polis Chrysochous	Paphos	Cyprus
Ayia Thekla	Sotira	Famagusta	Cyprus
Alcudia	Alcudia	Islas Baleares	Spain
Sant Elm	Andratx	Islas Baleares	Spain
Camp de Mar	Andratx	Islas Baleares	Spain
Colonia de San Pere	Arta	Islas Baleares	Spain
Benicassim	Benicassim	Castellon	Spain
Cala Baladrar	Benissa	Alicante	Spain
Playa de La Fosa	Calpe	Alicante	Spain
Palma Nova	Calvia	Islas Baleares	Spain
Es Trenc	Campos	Islas Baleares	Spain
Cala Agulla	Capdepera	Islas Baleares	Spain
Cala Ratjada	Capdepera	Islas Baleares	Spain
Playa de Daimus	Daimus	Valencia	Spain
Muchavista	El Campello	Alicante	Spain
El Campello	El Campello	Alicante	Spain
Figueretas	Ibiza	Islas Baleares	Spain
Arenal	Llucmajor	Islas Baleares	Spain
Cala Blava	Llucmajor	Islas Baleares	Spain
Porto Cristo	Manacor	Islas Baleares	Spain

Playa de Muro	Muro	Islas Baleares	Spain
Aigua Blanca	Oliva	Valencia	Spain
Pollensa	Pollensa	Islas Baleares	Spain
Sa Coma	San Llorenç	Islas Baleares	Spain
Espalmador	Sant Francesc	Islas Baleares	Spain
Sant Francesc	Sant Francesc	Islas Baleares	Spain
Can Picafort	Santa Margarita	Islas Baleares	Spain
Santa Pola	Santa Pola	Alicante	Spain
El Pinet	Santa Pola	Alicante	Spain
Sa Colonia	Ses Salines	Islas Baleares	Spain
Es Dolç	Ses Salines	Islas Baleares	Spain
Cala Millor	Son Servera	Islas Baleares	Spain
Villajollosa	Villajollosa	Alicante	Spain